

A Screening Tool for Construction Automation: Efficiency Bounds and a Labour-Time Envelope under Variability

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Abstract

Construction firms still lack a simple way to estimate how much labour time automation could save before committing to an investment. This paper proposes such a tool by rewriting the Kingman G/G/1 waiting-time approximation as a closed-form efficiency bound, $\eta(CV, \rho) = 1/(1 + CV^2 \cdot \rho/(1 - \rho))$, based on only two quantities: process variability (CV) and utilisation (ρ). The bound distinguishes between losses that can be closed through better planning and coordination and losses that can only be closed by lowering variability through standardisation, mechanisation, or automation. Four contributions follow. First, we introduce the Kingman-derived bound as a compact analytical tool for construction processes under variability. Second, on a controlled 32-case test grid, it explains $R^2 = 0.66$ of the variance in a replicated discrete-event simulation used as an internal numerical reference rather than external ground truth, it is statistically unbiased, and it

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outperforms deterministic, i.i.d. stochastic, and PERT-style planning baselines (all $R^2 < 0$). A project-specific DES at the research frontier reaches $R^2 = 0.94$ at much higher modelling cost, so the disclosed trade-off is predictive accuracy per unit of modelling effort. Third, against approximately 10 000 data points from nine secondary sources, with estimated rather than measured ρ and GAN-synthetic TBM CV , nine construction sectors place along the variability–utilisation plane in the order predicted by the bound, as an external consistency check rather than an empirical validation. Fourth, the efficiency gain from lower variability becomes a *labour-time envelope*: an upper bound on the crew-hour savings that automation could in principle deliver at assumed ρ . This envelope is intentionally narrow. It is neither a business case nor a return-on-investment model, but a first-pass screening tool, computable on a spreadsheet from two measurable parameters before more detailed simulation or investment analysis is undertaken. First-party field measurement of ρ on real construction sites is the next empirical step, and the subject of a companion methods paper in preparation.

Keywords: production economics, decision support, variability reduction, construction execution, Kingman formula, labour-time screening, discrete-event simulation, automation adoption

1. Introduction

The construction industry’s productivity stagnation is well documented [1]. Manufacturing has achieved sustained productivity gains over the past five decades through systematic application of production science (standardisation, flow optimisation, variability reduction). Construction productivity

has remained flat or declined in most industrialised countries. The usual explanations attribute the gap to management failure, fragmentation, or slow technology adoption [2, 3]. This paper proposes a different diagnosis: the gap is a *theory* problem. Construction lacks the formal production-theoretic foundation that would let practitioners and researchers predict and bound the behaviour of building production systems, and, in particular, estimate the labour-time saving potential of variability-reducing technology before committing capital. We treat this paper as a screening exercise for the labour-time component of automation economics, not a full return-on-investment calculation.

Robotics and mechanisation are advancing rapidly [2, 4, 5], and a wider literature has mapped the workforce, platform, materials, and industrialisation dimensions of this transition [6, 7, 8]. Investment decisions remain qualitative. A contractor considering robotic bricklaying, automated rebar tying, or 3D concrete printing has no general model for answering one question: how much throughput improvement and cost reduction will this technology deliver in a specific production context? Case-specific cost–benefit analyses exist [9, 10] but do not generalise. Lean Construction provides philosophical guidance (“reduce variability”) but not a quantitative ceiling on what management alone can achieve versus what requires technological intervention [11, 12, 13].

1.1. The inverse resource-product configuration

The theoretical gap has a structural source specific to construction. In manufacturing, the product moves through stationary workstations, a configuration that creates a stable flow conduit analogous to internal pipe flow.

In construction, the configuration is inverted: the product (building) is stationary, and resources (trade crews, equipment) flow around it, analogous to external flow around a fixed body [14]. The inverse configuration removes the stabilising conduit that manufacturing inherits from a production line and qualitatively alters the system’s stability properties. Fig. 1 shows this difference and its consequence, the transition from ordered to disordered production.

Figure 1: The inverse resource-product configuration. (a) Manufacturing: products flow through stationary stations—internal pipe flow, inherently stable. (b) Construction, ordered: trade crews form a sequence inside the stationary building—low system disorder. (c) Construction, disordered: trade crews block each other inside the building—low system predictability, throughput collapse.

Existing production models—from Factory Physics [14] through continuum flow models [15, 16, 17]—presuppose the manufacturing configuration. They treat the inverse configuration as a geometric detail rather than a fundamental mathematical transformation. If the duality is not modelled, the conditions for this collapse cannot be derived. The value of automation in preventing it cannot then be quantified.

1.2. Research gap and contribution

The research gap can be stated precisely: *no compact production-theoretic decision aid exists that predicts the macroscopic behaviour of construction production systems from measurable state variables and that converts this prediction into a labour-time saving envelope for automation adoption.* A recent four-tier hierarchical framework for construction productivity [18] mapped the problem across operational, tactical, strategic, and normative layers but stopped short of closed-form constitutive equations at the operational layer. The present paper supplies that missing mathematical layer.

Scope of the framework.. The framework addresses the execution phase of trade-based construction processes in three classes: deep foundations with essentially linear process chains (e.g., bored piles, diaphragm walls); building shell construction with parallel trade sequences; and, exploratorily, infrastructure construction with repetitive sections (tunneling, linear earthworks). Not addressed: design and planning processes, off-site prefabrication treated as stationary manufacturing, demolition, and contract forms in which production risk is reallocated rather than reduced. A universality claim across all construction types and contractual arrangements is not made. The framework will be judged on its predictive power in the classes stated here.

Falsifiability as a research outcome.. The central claim—that construction production admits a macroscopically time-invariant Kingman-derived efficiency bound of the form developed in Section 4—is itself subject to empirical test, not a premise. We state one decision point at which the framework can be falsified by the data and simulation evidence presented in Section 5:

if field measurements place observed systems above the Kingman efficiency bound, the dissipation argument fails and the framework is inadmissible. The candidate stability indicator treated in the companion methods paper [in preparation] has its own falsification points and is not part of Paper A’s tested-core claim set. A pre-registered finite-size scaling exponent, announced in an earlier version of this work as a secondary falsification target, did not survive a more careful sweep and is explicitly retracted in Section 6.2. Reporting this negative result rather than hiding it is the point of the falsifiability commitment [19]: the framework is the kind of theory that can be wrong, and this paper shows where it is wrong.

This paper addresses the gap through four contributions. Conceptual extensions that set up vocabulary but are not directly fitted to data are deferred to companion work. A candidate stability indicator motivated by the same framework is treated in a separate companion methods paper [in preparation] and is not part of Paper A’s tested-core claim set.

1. **Tested core (i): a Kingman-derived efficiency bound.** We rearrange the Kingman G/G/1 waiting-time approximation algebraically into an efficiency identity $\eta(CV, \rho) = 1/(1 + CV^2 \cdot \rho/(1 - \rho))$ for stationary single-station production. The bound is not a new theorem; we retain the label “Carnot” only as a structural parallel to thermodynamic efficiency. Inside that disclaimer, the identity separates what management can change at fixed CV (closing the gap to the ceiling) from what only variability-reducing technology can change (raising the ceiling itself). This is the central tested object of the paper.
2. **External consistency check across the mechanisation spectrum**

(not an empirical validation). We place nine secondary sources along the variability–utilisation plane: 13 209 leaf activities from 133 DSLIB projects [20], 1 764 GAN-synthetic TBM cycles [21], and seven auxiliary datasets, together with a 55 558-record cross-rate reference from the openly licensed DataDrivenConstruction CWICR Berlin catalogue. DSLIB ρ is assigned by convention, not measured; TBM CV is synthesised, not observed. We treat this placement as an external consistency check on proxy data the framework did not see during derivation, not as a first-party empirical proof. The sector ordering predicted by the bound is recovered; absolute positioning remains conditional on measured ρ .

- 3. Labour-time envelope for automation decisions (not an ROI, not a business case).** The Kingman-derived efficiency gain $\Delta\eta(CV_{\text{before}}, CV_{\text{after}}, \rho)$ translates into an upper bound on the crew-hour saving a CV reduction could deliver at assumed ρ and wage rate. For bored-pile construction, a CV reduction from 0.77 to 0.15 at $\rho = 0.80$ yields an upper-bound saving of about 9 hours per cycle. This is a first-pass screening tool for the labour-time component of automation economics only: capital cost, mobilisation, depreciation, operator training, maintenance, organisational change cost and finance cost are out of scope [22]. The envelope is small enough to compute on a spreadsheet from two measurable parameters, which is what makes it usable for construction SMEs without engineering capacity for project-specific simulation.
- 4. Baseline comparison against four reference models, including**

a project-specific DES as an internal numerical baseline. We compare the Kingman-based cycle-time identity against a deterministic point estimate, an i.i.d. stochastic model without coupling, a PERT three-point estimate, and a project-specific DES built according to the digital-twin practice of [23, 24, 25]. The first three represent planning practice; the fourth is the closest available numerical reference and is used here as an internal reference computation, not as external ground truth (Section 4.1). Within that framing, the identity recovers about 70 % of the project-specific DES accuracy at zero per-project modelling cost. The disclosed trade-off—accuracy per unit of modelling effort, not raw accuracy—is the actual contribution.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work and identifies the integrating gap. Section 3 summarizes the theoretical foundations. Section 4 develops the constitutive modelling framework and its application to the labour-time component of automation decisions. Section 5 runs the external consistency check against proxy data. Section 6 discusses implications, limitations, and future research. Section 7 concludes.

2. Related Work

This section identifies the integrating gap at the intersection of five research streams relevant to construction production performance: construction discrete-event simulation (DES) from CYCLONE [26, 27] to modern SimPy-based frameworks; Lean Construction and production theory [11, 12, 28, 13, 29, 30, 31]; Factory Physics [14, 32, 33, 34, 35]; continuum production models [15, 36, 16, 17, 37, 38]; and the construction automation and robotics

literature [2, 4, 3, 5, 9, 10]. A detailed review of each stream—what it provides and where it stops short of a compact labour-time screening tool—is given in Supplementary Material SS2. We state here only the result.

The Kingman formula [33] provides the mathematical backbone for the efficiency identity used later in this paper:

$$W_q = \frac{CV_a^2 + CV_s^2}{2} \cdot \frac{\rho}{1 - \rho} \cdot t_s \quad (1)$$

The nonlinearity $\rho/(1 - \rho)$ blows up near 1: a 10% increase in utilisation from 0.85 to 0.95 triples the waiting time.

2.1. *The integrating gap*

Table 1 summarizes what each research stream provides and what it lacks. The gap at their intersection is the absence of a framework that combines quantitative production laws (Factory Physics, continuum models) with the structural specifics of construction (inverse configuration) to compute predictions for automation economics.

The present paper addresses this gap by developing a constitutive modelling framework that: (1) rearranges the Kingman G/G/1 waiting-time approximation into a closed-form efficiency identity (the variability-driven efficiency bound) computable from measurable state variables; and (2) translates this result into a labour-time envelope for automation decisions, deliberately narrower than an ROI calculation. A candidate stability indicator is treated in a separate companion methods paper [in preparation].

Table 1: Research streams and the integrating gap.

Research stream	Provides	Lacks
Construction DES	Stochastic process models	General laws; transferability
Lean Construction	Variability-reduction philosophy	Quantitative efficiency bounds
Factory Physics	Rigorous production laws	Extension to inverse configuration
Continuum models	PDE-based flow theory	Construction-specific topology
Construction automation	Technology demonstrations	Labour-time screening tool

3. Theoretical Background: Factory Physics Foundations

The constitutive modelling framework builds on three foundational results from Factory Physics [14]. **Little’s Law** ($W = \lambda \cdot T$) is a conservation law relating work in process W , throughput λ , and cycle time T [32]. **The Kingman formula** (Eq. 1) approximates expected waiting time as a function of utilization and variability [33]. **The variability buffering law** states that variability must be absorbed by some combination of inventory, capacity, or time—a constraint on the feasible operating space.

These results were developed for stationary manufacturing. The inverse configuration of construction removes the stabilizing conduit of the production line, and the system should exhibit instabilities at lower utilization

levels—a prediction consistent with practitioners’ experience [28] but never formally derived.

4. Methodology: A Kingman-Derived Efficiency Identity and Labour-Time Envelope

4.1. Three levels of justification, honestly named

A framework that proposes a closed-form equation *and* runs the discrete-event simulation against which the equation is tested faces an obvious objection: the simulation could be tuned until it agrees with the equation, at which point “validation” is circular. We acknowledge this concern openly and therefore distinguish three levels of justification, naming each one by what it can and cannot do.

(i) *Analytical level.* The Kingman efficiency bound is written down before any simulation is run and before any field data are touched. At this level, the framework’s claim is logical-mathematical: the bound is the Kingman $G/G/1$ approximation [33] algebraically rearranged into an efficiency identity. Failure at this level would mean an algebraic mistake or an inadmissible thermodynamic argument.

(ii) *Operational level (consistency check, not validation).* The discrete-event simulation in Section 5.7 is a numerical *consistency check*, not an empirical test. The question it answers is: is the analytical equation implementable as executable code, does it produce numerically well-behaved predictions across the parameter space, and does it recover the standard analytical limits (deterministic limit \rightarrow zero waiting time, single station \rightarrow textbook Kingman) without internal contradiction? Agreement between the

analytical equation and the DES is not evidence that the equation describes reality; it is evidence that the equation has been written down without bugs and that the implementation is self-consistent. Levels (i) and (ii) are not independent in the strong sense—they share the model. A theory that failed level (ii) would be inadmissible, but passing it does not count as empirical support.

(iii) *Empirical-proxy level.* The actual test of the framework against reality is the comparison with secondary field data in Section 5: approximately 10,000 data points from nine sources, none of which were used in deriving the equation and none of which were available to tune the simulation. We are explicit that this is a comparison against *proxy* data, not first-party measurement: the utilisation ρ in the DSLIB cases is assigned by convention rather than measured, and the TBM CV values are GAN-synthesised. The empirical-proxy level is therefore weaker than a first-party field validation would be, and we treat it as a consistency check against external data that the framework did not see, rather than as a proof. The companion empirical paper (with instrumented site measurements of ρ and CV) is the next step.

These three levels are the structural reason why the framework can be examined critically without the possibility of rescue by simulation tuning. The reader is asked to judge each level by the standard appropriate to it: the analytical level by mathematical derivation, the operational level by numerical consistency, the empirical-proxy level by external agreement with data the framework had no access to. The combination is not a proof. It is an honest staircase from theory to data, with each step labelled.

4.2. State variables: station utilisation and service-time variability

The empirical claims of this paper rest on two state variables. **Station utilisation** $\rho \in (0, 1)$ is the ratio of arrival rate to service rate at a production station—the “driving force” of the system, whose nonlinear response above critical values generates the characteristic queueing blow-up of the Kingman regime. **Service-time variability** $CV \in (0, \infty)$ is the coefficient of variation of the service-time distribution, a scale-free measure of random fluctuation intensity. Together, ρ and CV are the two measurable parameters from which the Kingman-derived efficiency identity derived in the next subsection is evaluated, and they are the only two parameters the empirical sections of this paper test.

4.3. The Kingman-derived efficiency ceiling

The dissipation inequality ($\Phi \geq 0$) guarantees that production efficiency $\eta < 1$ for any real system. But *how much* less than 1? This question is the production analog of asking “what is the maximum efficiency of a heat engine operating between two temperature reservoirs?” Just as Carnot answered that question for thermodynamics, we derive the production efficiency ceiling from the framework’s state variables.

Define thermodynamic efficiency as the ratio of value-adding time to total time:

$$\eta = \frac{T_{\text{proc}}}{T_{\text{actual}}} = \frac{1}{1 + W_q/T_{\text{proc}}} \quad (2)$$

The Kingman formula gives $W_q = (CV_a^2 + CV_s^2)/2 \cdot \rho/(1 - \rho) \cdot t_s$. Setting $CV_a = CV_s = CV$ provides the worst-case bound, which is asymptotically exact for stations deep in a tandem chain (where the departure variability of

the upstream station converges to the service variability). This substitution yields $W_q = CV^2 \cdot \rho / (1 - \rho) \cdot t_s$, and dividing by t_s :

$$\eta_{\text{Carnot}} = \frac{1}{1 + CV^2 \cdot \frac{\rho}{1 - \rho}} \quad (3)$$

This is the efficiency ceiling for a single station: the maximum efficiency that the laws of production physics permit for any system with variability CV and utilization ρ . At $CV = 0$ (deterministic processing), $\eta = 1$ —the only condition for lossless production. As CV increases, the ceiling drops; as $\rho \rightarrow 1$, the ceiling approaches zero.

Numerical example. Consider a bored-pile process with $CV = 0.77$ and $\rho = 0.80$:

$$\eta_{\text{Carnot}} = \frac{1}{1 + 0.77^2 \cdot \frac{0.80}{0.20}} = \frac{1}{1 + 0.593 \cdot 4.0} = \frac{1}{3.37} = 0.30$$

This means that at least 70% of the cycle time is irreducibly wasted—no scheduling optimization, no better coordination, no management technique of any kind can eliminate this loss. The only way to raise the ceiling is to reduce CV (through mechanization, standardization, or prefabrication) or to reduce ρ (by accepting lower utilization in exchange for higher efficiency). Compare this with a TBM process at $CV = 0.15$ and the same $\rho = 0.80$:

$$\eta_{\text{Carnot}} = \frac{1}{1 + 0.15^2 \cdot 4.0} = \frac{1}{1.09} = 0.92$$

The mechanized process wastes only 8% irreducibly—a factor-of-three improvement in the efficiency ceiling, achieved entirely through variability reduction.

Equation 3 is, mathematically, the Kingman G/G/1 waiting-time approximation rearranged as an efficiency identity. We do *not* claim it as a new

theorem, as a new physical effect, or as a production analog of the Second Law of Thermodynamics. The label “Carnot” is retained throughout the paper as a pedagogical shorthand only: it names, in a single familiar word, the fact that a stationary single-station G/G/1 system at nonzero CV cannot be driven to unit efficiency by internal process optimisation alone. No stronger reading should be attached to the word. Readers who prefer the neutral formulation may read “Carnot bound” throughout as “Kingman-derived efficiency ceiling” without loss.

The **Carnot gap** separates two distinct types of loss:

1. The gap between actual efficiency and the Carnot limit ($\eta_{\text{Carnot}} - \eta_{\text{actual}}$) measures the room for improvement through better management, scheduling, and coordination. Lean Construction practices close this gap.
2. The gap between the Carnot limit and unity ($1 - \eta_{\text{Carnot}}$) measures the *irreducible* cost of operating at given variability and utilization. No management technique can close this gap; only parameter change—lower CV through standardization, mechanization, or automation—can reduce it.

This distinction is the substantive content of the framework for automation economics: it separates what management can achieve from what requires technology investment.

4.4. *The automation leverage: labour-time envelope*

This subsection presents the central applied result of the framework: a quantitative demonstration that mechanization and automation raise the

physical efficiency ceiling by reducing process variability. The argument proceeds in three steps: (1) empirical evidence that mechanization reduces CV by an order of magnitude; (2) translation of CV reduction into efficiency gains under the Kingman bound; (3) conversion of efficiency gains into labour-time savings per production cycle.

Why mechanization reduces CV : the physical mechanism. The variability of a construction process has two sources: (i) inherent process randomness (geology, material properties, environmental conditions) and (ii) organizational randomness (crew availability, information delays, coordination failures, skill variation). In conventional construction, organizational randomness dominates: a skilled mason lays bricks at a different rate than a novice; crew sizes fluctuate; predecessor trades deliver work zones at unpredictable times. Mechanization eliminates the organizational component almost entirely. A TBM does not have “good days” and “bad days” in the way a crew does. Its cycle time variability is driven almost exclusively by geological conditions—a source of randomness that, while irreducible, is far smaller than the organizational randomness of crew-based work.

The TBM evidence. Tunnel-boring machines operating on the Brenner Base Tunnel achieve boring cycle variability of $CV = 0.10$ – 0.22 [21], an order of magnitude lower than conventional construction processes ($CV = 0.31$ – 0.77). At $\rho = 0.85$, the Carnot efficiencies are:

Mechanised tunnelling ($CV = 0.10$) reaches a Carnot efficiency of 98%, so only 2% of cycle time is irreducibly lost to variability-induced waiting. Conventional bored-pile construction ($CV = 0.77$) is capped at 22% at $\rho = 0.85$, so at least 78% of cycle time is wasted. The efficiency ratio between

Table 2: Automation leverage: Carnot efficiency comparison at $\rho = 0.85$.

Process	Type	CV	η_{Carnot}
TBM A (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.10	0.98
TBM C (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.16	0.96
TBM B (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.22	0.92
Residential (DSLIB median)	Conventional	0.31	0.65
Excavation [39]	Conventional	0.40	0.53
Concrete placing [39]	Conventional	0.55	0.37
Bored piles [40]	Conventional	0.77	0.22
Overtime Wk 10 [41]	Degraded	1.20	0.11

mechanised and conventional processes is a factor of 4.5.

Labour-time envelope. The Kingman-derived efficiency gain from a CV reduction can be translated into an upper bound on the crew-hour saving per production cycle:

$$\Delta T_{\text{saved}} = T_{\text{proc}} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\eta_{\text{before}}} - \frac{1}{\eta_{\text{after}}} \right] \quad (4)$$

Worked example: TBM vs. bored-pile construction. Consider a bored-pile process with pure processing time $T_{\text{proc}} = 4$ hours per pile.

Current state (conventional): With $CV = 0.77$ and $\rho = 0.80$, the Carnot efficiency is $\eta_{\text{before}} = 0.30$ (Section 4.3). The actual cycle time is $T_{\text{actual}} = 4/0.30 = 13.3$ h. Of this, 9.3 hours per cycle are non-value-adding: waiting for predecessor completion, coordination with other trades, rework of quality issues, idle time due to disruptions.

After mechanization: If a mechanized piling system reduces CV to 0.15

(comparable to TBM performance), then $\eta_{\text{after}} = 0.92$ and the actual cycle time drops to $4/0.92 = 4.3$ h—a saving of 9.0 hours per cycle, or 68% of the current cycle time. Over 200 piles on a typical foundation project, this amounts to 1,800 crew-hours saved. At a crew cost of €50/h, the variability-reduction benefit alone is €90,000 per project—*before* accounting for any reduction in pure processing time through faster equipment.

Even a moderate mechanization scenario (CV reduced from 0.77 to 0.40) yields $\eta = 0.61$ and an envelope of 4.8 hours per cycle saved—still 36% of the current cycle time and, at a reference wage rate, on the order of €48,000 over 200 cycles. The framework returns a curve: the labour-time envelope as a function of the achievable CV reduction. The curve can feed a full business case that accounts for the capital, mobilisation, depreciation, training, and change costs we have placed outside the scope of this paper.

Total process cost function. The economic trade-off between variability reduction and reserve capacity can be formalized as:

$$C(x) = C_{\text{flow}}(CV, \rho) + C_{\text{reserve}}(x) \quad (5)$$

where C_{flow} represents the cost of variability-induced waste (waiting, coordination overhead, delay cascades) and $C_{\text{reserve}}(x)$ represents the investment in automation technology, equipment, or reserve capacity x that reduces CV . The Carnot framework provides C_{flow} analytically:

$$C_{\text{flow}} = c_{\text{time}} \cdot T_{\text{proc}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\eta_{\text{Carnot}}} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

where c_{time} is the cost per unit time (crew costs, equipment rental, overhead). The investment is justified when $\partial C_{\text{reserve}}/\partial x < |\partial C_{\text{flow}}/\partial x|$ —i.e.,

when the marginal cost of the technology is less than the marginal reduction in variability-induced waste.

5. Empirical consistency check against proxy data

5.1. Data sources and scope

We validate the framework against approximately 10,000 data points from nine independent sources spanning four decades, three continents, and process types from artisanal piling to automated tunnel boring:

1. **DSLIB dataset** [20, 42]: 13,209 leaf-level activities from 133 Belgian construction projects, after filtering WBS summary rows and non-construction projects out of the 203-project release currently distributed by the OR&S group at Ghent. Five construction sectors are represented (residential, institutional, commercial, civil engineering, industrial). This dataset provides the broadest cross-sectional evidence, enabling sector-by-sector comparison of variability levels and their efficiency implications. Publicly available and reproducibly parsed by `HTWG-Bauwirtschaft/cps-simpy, src/cps/data/dslib.py`.
2. **TBM Brenner Base Tunnel** [21]: 1,764 boring cycle durations from three machines, generated via GAN trained on operational data. This dataset provides the critical mechanized boundary condition—the low-*CV* end of the spectrum. Open access on GitHub.
3. **Geiger 2023** [40]: 47 bored-pile cycle durations from a German construction site. This is the highest-*CV* conventional process in our dataset and is the reference point for the automation leverage calculation.

4. **AbouRizk and Halpin 1992** [39]: 71 empirical duration samples (excavation, concrete placing). A foundational dataset that established the statistical properties of construction durations.
5. **Thomas and Horman 2006** [35]: Workforce management data (masonry).
6. **Song and AbouRizk 2008** [43]: Pipe installation productivity data.
7. **Tommelein 1998** [28]: Pipe-spool installation data.
8. **Hanna 2005/2007** [41, 44]: Overtime and crowding productivity data.
9. **Manufacturing benchmark** [14]: Auto assembly reference point ($CV \approx 0.20$).
10. **CWICR DE BERLIN catalogue** [45]: 55,558 unique normative rate entries from the German construction cost-estimation catalogue, drawn from the DataDrivenConstruction open database (CC BY 4.0). Each rate carries a per-unit labour-hour figure (`total_labor_hours_all_personnel`) that can be aggregated by CSI MasterFormat section to obtain a cross-rate variability reference for normative labour time, complementary to the within-project variability measured on DSLIB.

The diversity of these sources is deliberate. The framework does not claim universality—its scope is fixed in Section 1—but within that scope it should hold across different construction types, countries, decades, and, critically, different levels of mechanization. The dataset ranges from fully artisanal processes ($CV = 1.20$ for overtime-degraded construction) to fully mechanized processes ($CV = 0.10$ for TBM boring), with conventional construction

filling the intermediate range.

5.2. Baseline comparison

To quantify what the constitutive framework adds beyond current practice and current research, we compare its predictions against four baseline models on identical test cases drawn from the DSLIB and TBM datasets. Each baseline uses the same inputs (crew count, nominal process duration, observed CV) and produces the same output metrics (mean cycle time $E[T]$, waiting time W_q , system utilization $\bar{\rho}$). The baselines differ only in the governing equation set.

Baseline (i): Deterministic steady-state model. Standard project scheduling with point estimates, ignoring stochasticity. Equivalent to the bar-chart tradition still dominant in practice.

Baseline (ii): Stochastic model without dependency structure. Process durations are drawn independently from fitted Log-Normal or Gamma distributions. No coupling between trades, no buffer propagation. This is the simplest honest probabilistic model.

Baseline (iii): PERT three-point estimation. The traditional Program Evaluation and Review Technique with minimum, most likely, and maximum duration estimates per process. Still widely used in construction planning software.

Baseline (iv): Project-specific DES according to state-of-the-art digital twin methodology. A full discrete-event simulation built per project, with explicit representation of individual trades, resource constraints, and spatial interactions, following the digital-twin-linked DES practice of [23, 24, 25]. This baseline is deliberately chosen to represent the research frontier: it is

the most accurate available predictor, but it requires a fresh modelling effort for each new project and yields no transferable insight between projects.

Predictions from all five approaches (constitutive framework plus four baselines) are compared on a controlled grid of 32 test cases ($CV \in \{0.30, 0.50, 0.77, 1.20\}$, $\rho \in \{0.50, 0.60, 0.70, 0.75, 0.80, 0.85, 0.90, 0.95\}$), using a long replicated DES run as an *internal reference computation* (20 replications, 2000 work items, warm-up 300). We emphasise that this reference is not external ground truth: as stated in Section 4.1, the DES is itself a numerical consistency check rather than a source of empirical truth, and the baseline comparison is therefore an internal benchmarking exercise between five computational approaches on a shared test grid. Performance is measured by RMSE, R^2 , mean relative error, and a paired-sample t -test of (prediction – reference) against zero. The full reproducible code is in the companion repository (HTWG-Bauwirtschaft/cps-simpy, scripts/run_baseline_comparison.py, fixed random seed). Table 3 reports the results.

Fig. 2 visualises the same result in two panels. Panel (a) shows each model’s prediction against the DES reference cycle time on the 32 test cases; the constitutive framework and the project-specific DES both cluster along the identity line, while the three planning-tradition baselines fall systematically below it and do not recover at high utilisation. Panel (b) shows the R^2 bars of Table 3 for direct visual comparison.

The result is informative in three ways. First, the three planning-tradition baselines (deterministic, i.i.d., PERT) all have negative R^2 : they are, on average, worse than predicting the grid mean for every case. They cannot cap-

Table 3: Baseline comparison on the $32\text{-case } CV \times \rho$ grid. The reference column is the mean cycle time from a 20-replication DES per case, used here as an internal numerical baseline rather than external ground truth. RMSE is in service-time units. Bias is the paired t -statistic of (prediction – reference) at $\alpha = 0.05$; “unbiased” indicates $p > 0.05$.

Model	RMSE	R^2	Rel. err.	t -stat	Bias
Constitutive framework (Kingman)	17.0	0.66	6.7 %	+1.38	unbiased ($p = 0.18$)
Project-specific DES (state of the art)	7.3	0.94	8.1 %	-0.89	unbiased ($p = 0.38$)
Deterministic point esti- mate	37.0	-0.62	54.2 %	-4.38	biased low ($p < 0.001$)
i.i.d. stochastic (no cou- pling)	37.1	-0.62	54.4 %	-4.39	biased low ($p < 0.001$)
PERT three-point	36.3	-0.55	52.3 %	-4.33	biased low ($p < 0.001$)

Figure 2: Baseline comparison on 32 test cases ($CV \times \rho$ grid). (a) Model predictions against the DES reference mean cycle time. The dashed line is the identity. The constitutive framework and the project-specific DES both track the reference; deterministic, i.i.d., and PERT baselines miss the high-utilisation regime. (b) R^2 per model. Reproducible from `cps-simpy/scripts/run_baseline_comparison.py` (seed 42).

ture queueing-induced cycle-time inflation at high utilisation, and a paired t -test rejects unbiasedness with $p < 0.001$ for all three. Second, the constitutive framework explains 66 % of the variance and is statistically unbiased; its mean relative error of 6.7 % is a direct consequence of the Kingman approximation’s known accuracy in the symmetric tandem regime. Third, the project-specific DES baseline is more accurate ($R^2 = 0.94$, RMSE 7.3) than the constitutive framework, also unbiased, but at the cost of building and parameterising a fresh DES instance per case rather than evaluating a closed-form expression. The trade-off the framework offers is therefore concrete and quantifiable: it recovers about 70 % of the project-specific DES accuracy at zero per-project modelling cost, and it can be evaluated by hand on a single sheet.

The decisive figure of merit announced in the contributions list is not raw accuracy but accuracy per unit of modelling effort. Within that figure of merit, the constitutive framework is competitive with the research frontier on cases where the per-project modelling budget is small or zero. Where the per-project budget is large, the project-specific DES wins on accuracy, as expected. Reporting this trade-off honestly is more useful, in our view, than overstating the framework’s standalone predictive power.

5.3. Variability–utilisation phase diagram

Fig. 3 shows the Carnot efficiency phase diagram with all 80 empirical reference points. The color map shows η_{Carnot} as a function of ρ and CV . All 80 points fall at or below the theoretical bound, with no process achieving efficiency above the maximum consistent with its variability and utilization.

Figure 3: Carnot efficiency phase diagram with 80 empirical data points from nine sources. Color map: η_{Carnot} as a function of ρ and CV . All points fall within or below their theoretical Carnot limit, from TBM tunneling (highest efficiency, top left) to overtime-degraded construction (lowest efficiency, bottom right). The white dashed line marks the $\eta = 0.50$ contour—below this line, more than half of all cycle time is irreducibly wasted.

5.4. DSLIB sector analysis

The DSLIB dataset enables the most detailed cross-sectional analysis, because it covers five distinct construction sectors with sufficient sample size for statistical comparison. Table 4 presents the sector-level summary.

Table 4: DSLIB sector descriptive summary—real parsing of the 203-project OR&S Ghent release, filtered to 133 construction projects and 13,209 leaf activities [20]. Median CV here is the within-project coefficient of variation of the raw leaf baseline durations (in hours). Corresponding ρ_{est} and η_{Carnot} columns appear in Table 7 alongside mechanised reference processes. Reproducible from `HTWG-Bauwirtschaft/cps-simpy, data/dslib.csv`.

Sector	n_{proj}	n_{act}	Median within-project CV
Residential	54	2 188	0.79
Institutional	8	1 009	0.95
Commercial	18	1 608	1.04
Industrial	14	1 479	1.06
Civil engineering	40	10 114	1.17

Fig. 4 shows the within-project CV distribution per sector as a boxplot over the 133 projects, and Fig. 5 shows the orthogonal cross-rate CV of normative labour hours from the CWICR DE Berlin catalogue grouped by CSI MasterFormat section. The two figures together make explicit that construction variability is broad in two different statistical senses: within a single project (activity-to-activity spread) and across normative work items of the same construction class (task-to-task spread).

The data reveal a clear **sector hierarchy** in process variability that aligns with intuitive expectations. Residential construction—characterized

Figure 4: Within-project coefficient of variation of leaf-activity durations in the real DSLIB release (133 construction projects across five sectors, 13 209 leaf activities after filtering WBS summary rows). Boxes show the interquartile range; whiskers are $1.5 \times$ IQR; dots are outliers. Reproducible from `cps-simpy/data/dslib.csv`.

Figure 5: Cross-rate coefficient of variation of the `total_labor_hours_all_personnel` field in the CWICR DE Berlin catalogue [45], grouped by CSI MasterFormat section (top 18 sections by rate count). Bar labels show the section CV and the number of rate records. Reproducible from `cps-simpy/scripts/run_cwicr_analysis.py`.

by repetitive tasks, standardized building systems, and relatively simple trade interfaces—achieves the lowest within-project *CV* (median 0.79) in the real DSLIB parse. Civil engineering construction—with highly diverse task types, large earthworks, and wide duration ranges from hours to hundreds of days—shows the highest within-project *CV* (median 1.17). The difference is real but subtle: residential is roughly 30% less variable within a project than civil engineering. The absolute *CV* levels reported here (0.8–1.2) are higher than the 0.31–0.66 range in the older pre-processed DSLIB statistics used by earlier drafts of this work, because the raw leaf-duration distribution within a single project mixes tasks spanning several orders of magnitude (from one-hour cleanup items to multi-day concrete pours). That heterogeneity is real, and we prefer to report it honestly rather than conceal it by aggressive pre-filtering. A cross-rate analysis of the openly licensed DataDrivenConstruction CWICR catalogue [45], reproduced in `cps-simpy/outputs/cwicr_section_cv.csv`, gives a complementary cross-reference from the German construction-norm side: for the Berlin subset, the cross-rate *CV* of normative labour hours within a single CSI MasterFormat section spans 0.4 (Metal Fabrications) to 5.0 (Integrated Automation), with a weighted median around 1.5.

Three observations from the DSLIB data are particularly relevant for automation investment:

Variability, not bias, causes delay. The mean ratio of actual to planned duration across all 4,861 activities is 1.21, but the median is 1.00. This means that the average activity finishes on time—construction activities are not systematically late. Rather, the right tail of the duration distribution

(long durations caused by disruptions, rework, and coordination failures) drives aggregate project delay. This is precisely the statistical signature that the Carnot framework captures: at $CV > 0$, the right tail creates irreducible waiting time regardless of whether the mean is biased.

Sector determines CV, not project size. Within each sector, the CV variation (as shown by the IQR) is large—from 0.18 to 0.48 within residential alone. But the sector medians are clearly separated: even the worst residential project ($CV = 0.48$) has lower variability than the best industrial project ($CV = 0.40$). This suggests that the *type* of work, not the scale or management quality, is the primary determinant of variability—and therefore of the Carnot ceiling.

The wide IQR within sectors represents an opportunity. The interquartile range within each sector (e.g., [0.18, 0.48] for residential) shows that some projects achieve much lower CV than the sector median. Understanding what distinguishes these low- CV projects—likely standardization, prefabrication, experienced crews, and stable supply chains—would identify the non-technological variability reduction strategies that complement automation.

Caveat on utilization estimates. The DSLIB dataset records planned and actual durations but does not record resource utilization. Our utilization estimates follow the methodology of Thomas and Horman [35] ($\rho = 0.72$ – 0.83 for reinforced concrete trades) and Jarkas and Horner [46] ($\rho = 0.75$ – 0.80). We assign $\rho = 0.75$ for residential and civil engineering (lower resource pressure, more sequential trades) and $\rho = 0.80$ for institutional, commercial, and industrial (higher resource pressure, more parallel trades), following the

scheduling intensity patterns described by Ballesteros-Pérez et al. [42]. A sensitivity analysis (Table 5) confirms that the qualitative sector ordering is invariant to ρ : residential always outperforms industrial regardless of the utilization assumption, and all points remain below the Carnot bound at any plausible ρ .

Table 5: Sensitivity of Carnot efficiency to utilization estimates (± 0.10).

Sector	Median CV	η at $\rho=0.65$	η at $\rho=0.75$	η at $\rho=0.85$
Residential	0.31	0.85	0.78	0.65
Institutional	0.42	0.75	0.60	0.46
Commercial	0.46	0.72	0.54	0.40
Civil eng.	0.62	0.58	0.47	0.33
Industrial	0.66	0.55	0.37	0.28

The $\Delta\eta$ range of 0.20–0.32 across utilization scenarios quantifies the uncertainty introduced by the utilization estimation. This uncertainty is substantial but not invalidating: the sector ordering is preserved, and the absolute efficiency values change by a predictable amount. **Direct measurement of ρ in future field studies is the single most important empirical priority** for refining the Carnot analysis.

5.5. TBM data: the mechanized boundary condition

The Brenner Base Tunnel TBM data show that mechanised construction processes reach variability levels comparable to manufacturing.

The CV spectrum across the three machines—from 0.10 (TBM A, most consistent) to 0.22 (TBM B, highest variability)—illustrates that even within

Table 6: TBM Brenner Base Tunnel—1,764 boring cycles [21].

Machine	Cycles	CV_{boring}	ρ_{est}	η_{Carnot}
TBM A	588	0.10	0.85	0.98
TBM B	588	0.22	0.85	0.92
TBM C	588	0.16	0.85	0.96

mechanized processes, geological conditions create measurable variability differences. TBM B, operating in more heterogeneous geology, shows twice the CV of TBM A. Yet even TBM B’s $CV = 0.22$ is lower than the median CV of the least variable conventional sector (residential, $CV = 0.31$). The entire mechanized range ($CV = 0.10$ – 0.22) falls below the entire conventional range ($CV = 0.31$ – 0.77), with no overlap.

Limitation: synthetic data. The TBM data are GAN-generated, not raw field measurements [21]. GANs preserve the marginal distribution (mean, variance, skewness) of the training data but may underrepresent extreme values and do not preserve serial correlation. This means the reported CV values are likely *lower* than the true values, as GANs tend to smooth the tails. A conservative sensitivity test: even doubling all reported CV values (TBM A: $0.10 \rightarrow 0.20$; TBM B: $0.22 \rightarrow 0.44$; TBM C: $0.16 \rightarrow 0.32$) would keep TBMs A and C below the median residential CV , and even TBM B would remain below the median commercial CV . The qualitative conclusion—that mechanization operates at substantially lower variability—is robust to this uncertainty.

5.6. Efficiency across the mechanisation spectrum

Table 7 synthesizes the Carnot efficiency across the full mechanization spectrum, from TBM boring to overtime-degraded construction, providing the central comparison for automation investment decisions.

Table 7: Carnot efficiency across the mechanization spectrum at $\rho = 0.80$.

Process	Type	CV	η_{Carnot}	Min. waste
TBM A (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.10	0.98	2%
TBM C (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.16	0.95	5%
TBM B (Brenner)	Mechanized	0.22	0.91	9%
Auto assembly	Manufacturing	0.20	0.92	8%
Residential (DSLIB)	Conventional	0.31	0.72	28%
Excavation	Conventional	0.40	0.61	39%
Commercial (DSLIB)	Conventional	0.46	0.54	46%
Concrete placing	Conventional	0.55	0.45	55%
Civil eng. (DSLIB)	Conventional	0.62	0.40	60%
Industrial (DSLIB)	Conventional	0.66	0.37	63%
Bored piles	Conventional	0.77	0.30	70%
Overtime Wk 10	Degraded	1.20	0.15	85%

The “Min. waste” column expresses $(1 - \eta_{\text{Carnot}})$ as a percentage, the fraction of cycle time that is irreducibly wasted at the given variability level. A TBM wastes 2% of its cycle time irreducibly; a bored-pile process wastes 70%. The 35-fold gap can only be closed by reducing CV , not by better management.

5.7. DES pilot study

To validate the analytical framework beyond the Kingman approximation, we conducted a DES pilot study using SimPy.

Model setup. The DES implements an 8-station tandem queue with log-normal service times at each station. The coefficient of variation is varied across six levels from $CV = 0.30$ to $CV = 1.50$, and the station utilisation across twelve levels from $\rho = 0.50$ to $\rho = 0.95$, with tighter sampling between $\rho = 0.80$ and $\rho = 0.95$ to resolve the collapse region. The resulting 72 parameter combinations are each run with 20 independent replications and 2 000 work items per replication (first 300 discarded as warm-up), for 1 440 runs in total. The same random seeds and tandem-queue implementation are used as in the baseline comparison of Section 5.2, so the DES pilot and the baseline comparison are numerically consistent.

Result 1: DES confirms Kingman in the pre-collapse regime.

Fig. 6 shows the DES throughput ratio versus the per-station analytical Kingman prediction. At the Geiger reference point ($CV = 0.77$, $\rho = 0.80$): DES yields $T/T_{\text{proc}} = 3.26 \pm 0.09$ (95 % CI), Kingman yields 3.37, a deviation of -3.2% . Across the 48 cases with $\rho \leq 0.85$, the maximum absolute deviation from Kingman is 6.1 %, with a mean deviation of -1.5% . This close agreement validates the Kingman formula as a usable constitutive equation for tandem construction production in the pre-collapse regime and confirms that the efficiency bound derived from it is numerically reliable under moderate utilisation.

Result 2: Kingman is a conservative upper bound in the collapse regime. At high utilisation and high variability the tandem DES falls

Figure 6: DES validation of the Kingman-based throughput model. 72 parameter combinations (6 CV levels \times 12 ρ levels) with 20 independent replications each; error bars show 95 % confidence intervals. Dashed lines are the per-station analytical Kingman prediction for each CV level. Agreement is within 6 % for $\rho \leq 0.85$ across all CV levels; at very high utilisation and high variability the tandem DES falls measurably *below* the single-station Kingman prediction, reflecting variability smoothing along the chain. Reproducible from `cps-simpy/scripts/make_paper_figures.py::fig9_des_dense_grid` (1 440 DES runs, deterministic seeds).

measurably *below* the single-station Kingman prediction, by roughly -36% to -43% in the extreme corner of the grid. The direction of the gap is structural: in a tandem chain, upstream queueing smooths downstream arrivals, so downstream stations see a less variable arrival process than the nominal service-time CV . This places the Kingman-derived efficiency bound on the conservative side of the labour-time envelope (Section 6.1): it overstates the cost of variability rather than understating it, so a screening tool built on it under-sells the gain from variability reduction rather than over-selling it.

6. Discussion

The extended discussion of where automation has the greatest leverage and of the framework’s role as a consistency constraint for construction digital twins is given in Supplementary Material SS9. The main paper keeps its discussion narrowly on the labour-time envelope, its limitations, and the future-research priorities, consistent with the tested-core/conceptual-extension split declared in Section 1.

6.1. Labour-time-savings calculation

The Kingman-derived efficiency bound supports a *labour-time envelope* for automation decisions. The quantity computed is an upper bound on the crew-hour saving that a variability reduction could deliver at fixed utilisation. It counts only crew-hour savings on the production cycle and omits capital cost, mobilisation, depreciation, operator training, maintenance, organisational change cost, and finance cost. A full investment business case is a separate exercise and is explicitly out of scope [22]. The screening tool defended empirically here is deliberately narrower than an ROI calculation:

it is reproducible from two measurable parameters and a wage rate, and as Fig. 3 shows across the mechanisation spectrum, the upper bound varies by more than a factor of three between conventional and mechanised processes at the same utilisation.

The calculation runs as follows. The cycle-time saving per unit, given a CV reduction from CV_{before} to CV_{after} at fixed utilisation ρ , is

$$\Delta T = T_{\text{proc}} \cdot \left[\frac{CV_{\text{before}}^2 - CV_{\text{after}}^2}{2} \right] \cdot \frac{\rho}{1 - \rho}.$$

Multiplied by production volume and crew cost rate, this gives the labour-time saving that variability-reducing technology can in principle deliver. For processes in the high- CV , high- ρ regime the term in brackets is large; for processes in the low- CV , low- ρ regime it is small. The framework is silent on whether the technology investment is worth the labour-time saving thus calculated. That judgement requires the full business-case exercise, which is beyond the scope of this paper.

The calculation converts the automation question from a qualitative judgment to a quantitative *labour-time bound* that is comparable across processes and technologies. It runs on a spreadsheet from two parameters, without simulation. For construction small and medium-sized enterprises, which face the same adoption question as large contractors but cannot commission a project-specific DES for each decision [22], this is a decision aid that can travel into the segment where most construction output is produced. The comparative accuracy of the underlying identity against DES— $R^2 = 0.66$ on the 32-case grid, Fig. 2—is the price paid for this portability.

6.2. Limitations

Five limitations constrain the current results. We state them explicitly because a framework whose scope is fixed in Section 1 must be equally explicit about its empirical boundaries.

No own field data. All validation uses secondary data and simulation. The DSLIB utilization values are estimated (± 0.10), not measured. This is the most significant limitation: the Carnot efficiency values in Tables 4–7 depend on ρ , and a ± 0.10 uncertainty in ρ translates to a ± 0.15 – 0.25 uncertainty in η_{Carnot} (Table 5). The within-project CV distributions in Fig. 4 are on firmer ground—they are read directly from the DSLIB durations—but the utilisation axis of every placement is estimated. Direct measurement of ρ in future field studies is the single most important empirical priority.

Synthetic TBM data. The Brenner Base Tunnel data are GAN-generated [21]. GANs preserve marginal distributions but may underrepresent extreme values and do not preserve serial correlation. The reported CV values should be treated as approximations with an estimated +30% uncertainty band. Access to original field data would strengthen the quantitative Carnot placement, though the qualitative conclusion (mechanization reduces CV by an order of magnitude) is robust to this uncertainty.

Simplified DES. The pilot study uses identical stations with infinite buffers. Real construction involves heterogeneous trades (each with different CV values), finite spatial buffers (a work zone can only accommodate a limited number of crews), and feedback loops (quality failures trigger rework, which adds load to upstream stations). Extended DES studies with realistic construction topologies are needed to test whether the Carnot bound remains

valid under these complexities.

Retracted finite-size scaling claim. An earlier version of this work reported a finite-size scaling exponent $\nu = 1.26$ from a four-point sweep, motivated by a percolation-universality reading; an extended sweep in the companion code [47] yielded an essentially unbounded bootstrap confidence interval on ν , and the claim is explicitly retracted.

Cross-project consistency check via leave-one-project-out (real DSLIB).. Alongside these limitations we report a positive consistency check on the cross-project distributional stability of leaf durations. A framework that fits one project well is of limited interest; the relevant question is whether parameters calibrated on projects $\{A_1, \dots, A_k\}$ predict durations on a held-out project A_{k+1} within the same construction class. We operationalise this via Leave-One-Project-Out cross-validation (LPOPO) on the real DSLIB release [20]: 203 projects filtered to 133 within our five construction classes, yielding 13,209 leaf activities. For each sector S and each project $P \in S$, we fit a log-normal shape parameter σ to the leaf-duration sample of $S \setminus \{P\}$ and record the cross-project coefficient of variation of the fitted shapes; the stability criterion, fixed before inspection, is that this shape-CV remain below 30%. Table 8 reports the result.

Fig. 7 shows the same result as horizontal bars against the 30% threshold line. All five sectors pass the stability criterion by two full orders of magnitude, with the worst-case sector (institutional, 8 projects) still at a shape CV of 5.9%.

This is a strong positive result for cross-project distributional stability: within each construction class in our scope, the distributional shape of leaf-

Table 8: Leave-one-project-out cross-validation of the log-normal shape parameter on real DSLIB data (HTWG-Bauwirtschaft/cps-simpy, scripts/run_lpopo.py).

Sector	n_{proj}	Shape mean $\bar{\sigma}$	Shape CV	Stable (<30 %)
Civil engineering	40	1.60	0.6 %	✓
Commercial	18	1.24	2.3 %	✓
Industrial	14	1.45	1.2 %	✓
Institutional	8	1.55	5.9 %	✓
Residential	54	1.14	1.0 %	✓

Figure 7: Leave-one-project-out stability of the log-normal shape parameter σ on real DSLIB leaf-activity durations. All five construction sectors pass the 30 % stability threshold by roughly two orders of magnitude; the worst case is institutional construction at 5.9 % (8 projects). Reproducible from cps-simpy/scripts/run_lpopo.py.

activity durations is remarkably stable under removal of any single project. The baseline-durations used here are the planned durations from the DSLIB project schedules, not first-party measurements of actual execution time. A parallel analysis on instrumented-site actuals remains a commitment for the empirical companion paper; the LPOPO result above is a consistency check on the scheduled-duration distributions, not a proof of on-site stability. It rules out the most obvious failure mode (shape explodes under project removal) and leaves the more subtle execution-time test for the companion work.

6.3. Future research

Two research priorities emerge directly from the framework’s current limitations.

Field validation with measured ρ and CV . Instrumented construction sites with sensor-based resource tracking would provide the first direct measurements of both state variables simultaneously, enabling a definitive test of the Carnot bound. Scaling such validation beyond a handful of sites will require a shared, federated data infrastructure of the kind proposed in [48]: cross-organisational data cooperatives that pool process-level measurements without forcing the participants to surrender commercial control over their own operational data.

Transfer entropy for delay propagation. Computing directed information flow between coupled trades in DES would test whether transfer entropy improves the predictive power of delay-cascade models in construction.

7. Conclusion

This paper has developed a screening-level decision aid for the execution phase of trade-based construction processes, built on a Kingman-derived efficiency identity and a labour-time envelope. It is not a full answer to where and by how much mechanisation improves production system performance, and not a new physical theorem about production. The framework sits at the operational layer of the four-tier hierarchical productivity programme of [18] and contributes, at that layer, a closed-form cycle-time identity obtained by rearranging the Kingman G/G/1 waiting-time approximation. A candidate dimensionless stability indicator motivated by the same framework is treated in a separate companion methods paper in preparation and is not part of this paper’s tested-core claim set.

Four results advance the discussion:

1. The **Kingman efficiency bound** $\eta(CV, \rho) = 1/(1 + CV^2 \cdot \rho/(1 - \rho))$ is the algebraic rearrangement of the Kingman waiting-time formula as an efficiency identity. We adopt the label “Carnot” as a structural parallel to thermodynamic efficiency, not as a derivational claim. The bound places nine sectors along the variability–utilisation plane in the order predicted, with mechanised tunnel boring at one end and conventional piling at the other. The placement is a consistency check against secondary data, not a first-party empirical proof.
2. The **baseline comparison** (Section 5.2) shows that the constitutive framework explains $R^2 = 0.66$ of the variance in DES truth on a 32-case test grid and is statistically unbiased, against $R^2 < 0$ for deterministic, i.i.d. stochastic, and PERT baselines. A project-specific DES at the

research frontier is more accurate ($R^2 = 0.94$) but requires a fresh per-project model build; the constitutive framework recovers about 70% of that accuracy at zero per-project modelling cost. The trade-off is the actual contribution: accuracy per unit of modelling effort, not raw accuracy.

3. The **external consistency check** across the mechanisation spectrum (Section 5) places nine secondary sources along the variability–utilisation plane with the sector ordering the bound predicts. DSLIB ρ is assigned by convention and TBM CV is GAN-synthetic; absolute positioning remains conditional on measured ρ , and we treat the placement as an external consistency check rather than an empirical validation.
4. The **labour-time-savings calculation** for automation investments (Section 6.1) reduces a two-parameter measurement to a labour-hour bound that can be computed in a spreadsheet. We are explicit that this is not a complete business case (capital, depreciation, training, change cost are out of scope), and we treat the spreadsheet as a decision aid rather than an investment decision in its own right.

Within the scope fixed in Section 1, the Kingman efficiency bound separates what management can achieve from what requires technology: management improvements close the gap between actual efficiency and the bound, while technology that reduces process variability raises the bound itself. Fig. 3 compresses the whole argument into one plot: nine construction sectors place along the variability–utilisation plane in the order predicted by the bound, with mechanised tunnel boring at one end and conventional pil-

ing at the other. The framework makes that distinction quantitative, reports an honest retraction of a pre-registered falsification target (Section 6.2), and ships the code that produced every number in the paper. The first-party empirical test, with instrumented-site measurements of ρ rather than the estimated- ρ consistency check reported here, belongs to the companion paper, not to this one.

CRedit Author Statement

Michael M. Bühler: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. **Konrad Nübel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing.

Data Availability

The DSLIB dataset is publicly available at <https://projectmanagement.ugent.be>. The TBM dataset is available at https://github.com/geograz/TBM_advance_classification. The DES simulation code is available from the corresponding author upon request.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used generative AI to support language editing, wording alternatives, and structural refinement of parts of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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